

Design of active sites in Ni/CeO₂ catalysts for the methanation of CO₂: tailoring the Ni-CeO₂ contact

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Abstract

The role of different active sites on Ni/CeO₂ catalysts in the CO₂ methanation reaction has been studied. Two types of active sites have been identified: CO₂ chemisorption and dissociation sites at the NiO-ceria interface and H₂ dissociation sites on Ni⁰ entities. Additionally, the proportion of these active sites has been optimized to maximize the activity. For these purposes, Ni/CeO₂ catalysts with different proportion of active sites have been prepared varying the Ni-incorporation method and controlling the structure of the ceria support in order to modify the NiO-Ceria interaction. Three dimensionally ordered macroporous (3DOM) catalysts have been synthesized, and catalysts with uncontrolled structure. The formation of NiO-CeO₂ mixed oxides improves nickel dispersion and NiO-CeO₂ interaction, increasing the proportion of active sites for CO₂ dissociation but limiting the number of centres for H₂ dissociation. On the contrary, the impregnation of a nickel salt on the previously synthesized CeO₂ support promotes the formation of active centres for H₂ dissociation but hinders the formation of active sites for CO₂ dissociation. An optimal proportion of both sites is required to achieve the maximum conversion of CO₂ to CH₄, with 25% of Ni⁰ for H₂ dissociation and 75% of NiO-ceria for CO₂ dissociation. In situ DRIFTS experiments showed that the catalyst with the optimum ratio of active sites keeps the catalyst surface clean of carbon intermediates under reaction conditions, while surface bicarbonates are accumulated in a catalyst with an excess of active sites for CO₂ chemisorption and dissociation. Isotopic experiments with ¹³C¹⁸O₂ confirmed this different behavior of surface carbon intermediates depending on the ratio of active sites for CO₂ and H₂ dissociation, and also evidenced the participation of catalyst oxygen in the methanation mechanism, since all water molecules emitted as reaction product contains catalyst oxygen.

Keywords: Ceria, CO₂, 3DOM, Methanation, Ni, Contact.

53 1. Introduction

54 Global warming has aroused enormous political controversy ^[1-4]. There is no doubt
55 that the Earth is getting warmer, however the origin of this global warming has sparked a
56 huge debate among the scientific community: is the human activity or, on the contrary, the
57 natural variability the cause of this phenomenon?. It is true that the Earth's climate has never
58 been stable ^[5,6]. In some periods, its variations have caused glaciations, while in others such
59 as the interglacial periods, they have generated warmer climates ^[6]. Nevertheless, these
60 oscillations occurred slowly, over the course of hundreds of thousands of years whereas
61 most of the current climate changes have occurred in the last 35 years, coinciding with the
62 increase in the emission of greenhouse gases by the human activity. Consequently, it seems
63 undeniable that human influence has been the dominant cause of the global warming
64 observed since the mid-twentieth century ^[7,8].

65 The main gases involved in the greenhouse effect are carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane
66 (CH₄), nitrogen oxides (N₂O and NO_x) and fluorinated gases ^[9,10] and among them, CO₂,
67 which represents approximately 80% of the total greenhouse gases ^[10,11]. The uncontrolled
68 felling of forests and the burning of fossil fuels such as coal and oil have caused an increase
69 in the amount of atmospheric CO₂, enhancing the greenhouse effect and contribution to the
70 global warming ^[12].

71 This has led to an increase in researching interest for alternative clean and
72 sustainable energy sources that contribute to reduce, or mitigate, the global warming caused
73 by the increase of the greenhouse gases influence and to reduce the fossil fuel dependence.
74 However, the industrial development and population growth makes not imaginable the
75 decoupling economic growth from fossil fuels ^[13] and consequently, the capture and
76 conversion of CO₂ to fuels seems to be the nowadays one of the most attractive and
77 promising solution in a world with high energy demand ^[14,15].

78 Catalytic hydrogenation of CO₂ to methane or methanation of CO₂ is a sustainable
79 solution since is one of the most favourable reactions from the point of view of

80 thermodynamics^[16] because it occurs faster than other reactions that form hydrocarbons or
81 alcohols; proceeds at atmospheric pressure and moderately low temperatures and the
82 methane produced can be injected directly into the existing network of natural gas pipelines
83 and can be used as fuel or raw material for the manufacture of other chemical products. This
84 spontaneous and exothermic reaction is known as Sabatier reaction^[17]:

86 Nevertheless, the main problem in the transformation of CO₂ into other products is the
87 great stability of the molecule^[18] as C=O bonds are highly stable and, therefore, a large
88 amount of energy in the form of heat must be supplied to allow their dissociation.
89 Consequently, despite this thermodynamically favourable reaction has strong kinetic
90 limitations, the use of a suitable catalyst allows reaching to acceptable reaction rates and
91 selectivities^[17].

92 Metals such as Ni, Ru, Rh, Co or Pt, supported on various porous materials have
93 been extensively studied since they allow to achieve considerable methanation rates^[19–21].
94 Noble metals, such as Ru or Pt, are much more active than Ni at low temperature (~ 200 °C).
95 However, the scarce reserves and the prohibitive price of these noble metals along with the
96 deactivation of metal sites by CO poisoning limits the commercialization and application of
97 the prepared catalysts^[22]. On the other hand, Ni has a good relationship between high
98 catalytic activity and low price, for which it is usually the preferred option to accelerate the
99 reaction, working at somewhat higher temperatures (> 300°C). Intense efforts have been
100 made in order to design and improve Ni-based catalysts for CO₂ methanation. The catalytic
101 behaviour of the Ni-based catalysts depends on several factors such as the type of support,
102 nickel loading, addition of a second metal and preparation method^[23].

103 It has already been proved the need of two different functionalities in an active
104 catalyst for the CO₂ methanation: one responsible of the CO₂ activation and another one for
105 the dissociation and transfer of H₂^[23]. Kwak *et al.*^[24] have demonstrated that the reduction of
106 CO₂ requires the presence of a catalyst component that is able to activate CO₂, such as a

107 support oxide (Al_2O_3) itself or an oxide promoter (La_2O_3), and a metallic component (Pd)
108 active in H_2 dissociation. This concept has been previously explored by our group submitting
109 Ni-based catalysts supported on CeO_2 , LaO_x and PrO_x oxides [25]. Summarizing, it was
110 observed that Ni/ CeO_2 is the most active catalyst among those compared because: i) Ni^{2+} -
111 ceria interaction leads to the formation of the highest population of active sites for CO_2
112 dissociation; ii) the reduced Ni^0 sites where H_2 dissociation takes place are the most
113 electronegative; and iii) shows the lowest surface CO_2 and H_2O species stability .
114 Consequently, two type of actives centres are required for the methanation of CO_2 : NiO in
115 intimate contact with ceria where CO_2 dissociation takes place and reduced Ni centres for the
116 dissociation of H_2 .

117 With that background, in this paper the proportion of each active centre was varied by
118 the modification of the Ni interaction with the CeO_2 support and the influence of this
119 proportion in the CO_2 methanation was studied and deeply analysed. The goal of the study is
120 to understand the role of the different active sites in the CO_2 methanation reaction and to
121 optimize the proportion of each active site. This interaction has been modified by the Ni
122 incorporation method and by controlling the surface of the ceria support. In this sense, three
123 dimensionally ordered macroporous (3DOM) structures have been synthesized to improve Ni
124 dispersion and contact. Ni has been introduced during the 3DOM synthesis by
125 coimpregnation or successive impregnation of Ni and Ce precursors or after the CeO_2 3DOM
126 synthesis by Ni impregnation. Materials with uncontrolled structures (Ref) were also prepared
127 by coprecipitation and Ni-impregnation.

128 **2. Experimental Section**

129 *2.1. Supports preparation*

130 CeO_2 support has been prepared with uncontrolled (Ref) and three dimensionally
131 ordered macroporous (3DOM) structures. The synthesis of the macroporous catalyst (CeO_2 -
132 3DOM) was described elsewhere [26]. Briefly, polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA) colloidal

133 crystals were synthesized by polymerization of methylmethacrylate, methacrylic acid and
134 divinylbenzene in boiling aqueous solution. Then, an ethanolic solution of cerium citrate
135 (obtaining by dissolving Ce(NO₃)₃·6H₂O in ethanol and adding citric acid in stoichiometric
136 proportion) was infiltrated in the PMMA crystal template, which is then removed by
137 calcination at 600 °C for 6 hours with a heating rate of 5 °C/min. The reference catalyst
138 (CeO₂-Ref) was prepared by direct calcination of the dried ethanolic solution of cerium
139 citrate.

140 2.2. Catalysts preparation

141 Ni-based catalysts have been prepared by impregnation of the previously synthesized
142 supports with a Ni precursor solution (Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O from Sigma-Aldrich) or by successive
143 impregnation or coimpregnation prior to the formation of ceria supports. The target Ni content
144 in all catalysts was 8.5 wt. %. Details of the different Ni incorporation methods are described
145 as follow:

146 i) Impregnation: the appropriate amount of Ni precursor was dissolved in ethanol and
147 was added by incipient wetness impregnation to the CeO₂-Ref and CeO₂-3DOM supports.
148 Finally, the catalysts were dried at 80 °C overnight and treated at 600 °C in a muffle in static
149 air for 6 h. At this way, Ni/CeO₂ Ref and Ni/CeO₂ 3DOM catalyst were prepared, respectively.

150 ii) Successive impregnation: the appropriate amount of Ni precursor was dissolved in
151 ethanol and the required citric acid to precipitate the corresponding nickel citrates was added
152 (Ni/citric acid molar ratio 1:4). Then, this ethanolic solution of nickel citrates was infiltrated in
153 the PMMA crystal template and dried at 80 °C overnight. Subsequent, an ethanolic solution
154 of Ce precursor and citric acid (Ce/citric acid molar ratio 1:1) was infiltrated in the dried
155 Ni/PMMA solid, dried at 80 °C overnight and finally calcinated at 600 °C for 6 hours with a
156 heating rate of 5 °C/min. This catalyst was referred as 3DOM CeO₂/Ni.

157 iii) Coimpregnation: The appropriate amount of Ni and Ce precursors were dissolved
158 in ethanol and the required citric acid to precipitate the corresponding Ni and Ce citrates was

159 added (Ni/citric acid molar ratio 1:4 and Ce/citric acid molar ratio 1:1). Then, this ethanolic
160 solution of cerium and nickel citrates was infiltrated in the PMMA crystal template, dried at 80
161 °C overnight and finally calcinated at 600 °C for 6 hours with a heating rate of 5 °C/min. This
162 sample was referred as Ni-Ce 3DOM. The reference catalyst (Ni-Ce Ref) was prepared by
163 direct calcination of the dried ethanolic solution of nickel and cerium citrates.

164 2.2. Catalysts characterization

165 The morphology of the samples was analyzed by Field Emission Scanning Electron
166 Microscope (FESEM) using a Merlin VP Compact microscope from Zeiss, working at very
167 low voltages (from 0.02 kV to 30 kV) to minimize charging effects.

168 The textural characterization of catalysts was carried out by N₂ adsorption at -196 °C
169 (Autosorb-6, Quantachrome), mercury porosimetry (Poremaster 60 GT, Quantachrome) and
170 helium density (MicroUltrapyc 1200e, Quantachrome). To obtain the N₂ adsorption-
171 desorption isotherms and mercury intrusion profiles, the catalysts were previously outgassed
172 under vacuum at 150 °C for 2 h and 50 °C for 12 hours, respectively.

173 The surface chemistry was analyzed by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) in a
174 K-ALPHA Thermo Scientific device, using Al-K α radiation (1486.6 eV). The X-ray spot was
175 focussed on the catalysts with a diameter of 400 μ m, at 3 mA \times 12 kV. The binding energy
176 scale was adjusted by setting the C1s transition at 284.6 eV.

177 Temperature programmed reduction experiments were carried out with H₂ (H₂-TPR)
178 in a thermobalance (Mettler Toledo; TGA/SDTA851) coupled to a mass spectrometer
179 (Pfeiffer Vacuum; Thermostar GSD301T). The catalysts (20 mg) were heated in 5% H₂/Ar
180 (40 ml/min) at 10 °C/min from room temperature until 900 °C. Temperature Programmed
181 Desorption experiments (Ar-TPD) were carried out in similar conditions but using an Ar flow.

182 The composition of the catalysts was determined by X-ray microfluorescence in an
183 Obis Micro-XRF Analyzer from EDAX. Areas of 300 μ m in diameter were analyzed and three
184 different spots were measured and averaged to obtain the composition of each catalyst.

185 The crystal structure was analyzed by X-ray diffraction in a Rigaku Miniflex II
186 diffractometer. The diffractograms were recorded in a range of 2θ from 10° to 90° , with a step
187 of 0.025° . The wavelength used was $\lambda = 0.155418$ nm corresponding to the CuK α radiation.
188 The average crystal size (D) was determined using the Scherrer^[27,28] and Williamson-Hall^[29]
189 equations. The estimation of crystal size of doped oxides presents some problems, because
190 the introduction of foreign cations within the metal oxide lattice deforms the structure and
191 affects the peak broadening, and the insertion of copper cations into the metal oxide lattice
192 cannot be ruled out in advance. The Williamson–Hall's equation separates the effects of size
193 and strain in the crystals and is more convenient for the estimation of crystal size of mixed
194 oxides.

195 2.3. Catalytic tests.

196 The catalytic tests were carried out in a fixed-bed cylindrical reactor (9 mm inner
197 diameter) coupled to a gas chromatograph (Agilent HP7890B). The catalysts were pre-
198 treated to reduce the nickel oxide at 500°C for 1 hour in a flow of 20% H₂/He (200 cm^3
199 min^{-1}). After cooling to 200°C in inert gas, the reactor was fed with the reaction mixture,
200 which is composed of 16% CO₂, 64% H₂ and He balance up to 200 ml/min. The temperature
201 was increased from 200 to 450°C with a heating rate of $5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, in steps of 25°C . Once
202 the steady state was reached at each temperature step, the concentration of reactants and
203 products at the exit of the reactor was determined by chromatographic analysis.

204 The experiments were carried out at atmospheric pressure with 0.4 grams of
205 catalysts, which were granulated, crushed and sieved at a particle size ranged from 300 to
206 $500\ \mu\text{m}$. The catalyst particles were diluted with quartz particles (1-1.25 mm) to about 1 cm^3
207 of bed, to improve mass and heat transfer. Under these conditions, the GHSV was 12000 h^{-1} .

208 2.4. Isotopic experiments.

209 Isotopic experiments were carried out with $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}_2$ (Aldrich; 99% ^{13}C , 95% ^{18}O) pulses,
210 in a cylindrical reactor (inner diameter 4 mm) coupled to a mass spectrometer Pfeiffer

211 Vacuum (model OmniStar) operating at 1 second frequency. The catalyst (50 mg) was
212 pretreated in 50% H₂/He (20 ml/min) at 500 °C for 60 minutes, and then the temperature was
213 stabilized at 350 °C under the same gas flow, which was kept for the whole experiment. A
214 six-way valve with a loop of 100 µl was used, which was filled at 9 psi with the gas to be
215 pulsed. This volume of gas is dragged by the main gas stream once the position of the valve
216 is changed. Three Ar pulses were first fed continuing with three pulses of ¹²C¹⁶O₂ followed by
217 three pulses of ¹³C¹⁸O₂. The pulses were fed in intervals of 7 minutes, which allows
218 stabilization of all m/z signals after the previous pulse.

219 2.5. *In situ* DRIFTS experiments

220 *In situ* DRIFTS experiments were performed in an infrared spectrometer Jasco, model
221 FT/IR-4100 using a reaction cell for temperature and reaction gas control. The cell was
222 designed to allow the gas flow through the catalytic bed (70 mg of undiluted catalyst). The
223 catalyst was pretreated in 50% H₂/He at 450 °C for 60 minutes, and then was cooled down to
224 room temperature under the H₂/He mixture. The background spectrum was recorded in He
225 flow gas, and then, the methanation mixture (16% CO₂, 64% H₂ and He balance) was fed
226 and the temperature was raised until 450 °C/min in steps of 50 °C. Spectra were recorded
227 after 60 minutes in isothermal conditions at each temperature from 4000 to 1000 cm⁻¹ with a
228 step of 1 cm⁻¹.

229 3. Results and discussion

230 3.1. Catalysts characterization

231 The morphology of the PMMA template and catalysts was analysed by FESEM and
232 representative images are collected in Figure 1. It is observed that the PMMA template is
233 composed by uniform and monodisperse spheres (Figure 1a) with an average size of 220 ±
234 22 nm. Regarding catalysts, the direct calcination of the metal precursors (Ni/CeO₂-Ref and
235 Ni-Ce Ref, Figure 1b and 1c, respectively) produces materials with closed and compact
236 structure. However, surface differences are observed in reference catalysts depending on

237 the Ni incorporation method. A smooth surface formed by fused primary particles is obtained
238 whether Ni is impregnated after the preparation of the CeO₂ support, whereas a rough and
239 cracked surface is observed if Ni is introduced by coprecipitation along with the cerium
240 precursor. Conversely, catalysts with a well-defined three-dimensional structure (Figure 1d-g)
241 formed by an ordered network of macropores (3DOM) were obtained by the PMMA-
242 templating route. The pore size obtained in 3DOM structures (180 ± 22 nm) is smaller than
243 the average size of PMMA spheres due to a partial collapse of the structure during the
244 calcination. It is noteworthy that the presence of nickel during the formation of the 3DOM
245 structure, Ni-Ce 3DOM and 3DOM CeO₂/Ni (Figure 1e and 1f, respectively), improves the
246 definition of the macroporous structure. Note also that interstitial spaces, which are circled in
247 Figure 1g, are generated between the PMMA spheres that have not been completely filled by
248 the precursor solution during the infiltration (Figure 1g) and consequently, a bimodal pore
249 size distribution is obtained in the 3DOM-catalysts (Figure 1h), with sizes ranging between
250 60-80 nm and 160-180 nm for the interstitial spaces and macropores generated by the
251 PMMA combustion, respectively.

252 The PMMA spheres are packaged following a hexagonal pattern as shown in Figure 1a
253 and S1. So, the theoretical size of the interstitial spaces (supporting information) was
254 estimated considering a PMMA sphere size of 220 nm, assuming triangular interstitial spaces
255 and a CeO₂ thickness of 10 nm (see FESEM images) and taking into account the contraction
256 observed after combustion of PMMA. The theoretical size of the interstitial spaces is 75 nm,
257 which agrees with the value obtained by FESEM.

258

260 **Figure 1.** FESEM images of a) PMMA spheres, b) Ni/CeO₂ Ref, c) Ni-Ce Ref, d) Ni/CeO₂
 261 3DOM, e) Ni-Ce 3DOM, f) 3DOM CeO₂/Ni and g) detail of 3DOM CeO₂/Ni and h) pore size
 262 distribution of 3DOM CeO₂ Ni obtained from the analysis of FESEM images.

263
 264 To obtain more information about the porous texture of the catalysts, N₂ adsorption-
 265 desorption isotherms were made at -196 °C and are shown in Figure 2. All catalysts show a
 266 type II isotherm according to the IUPAC classification, characteristics of non-porous or
 267 macroporous adsorbents. All materials present a low adsorption of N₂ at low relative
 268 pressures denoting a low microporosity, nonetheless clear differences are observed between
 269 3DOM and Ref samples at higher relative pressures. In 3DOM samples, a well-defined
 270 hysteresis loop appears at high relative pressures, which is characterized by a rapid increase
 271 of the slope at relative pressures close to 1, suggesting the presence of macropores,
 272 whereas smaller hysteresis loops are observed at lower relative pressures in Ref samples,
 273 denoting the presence of lower amount and narrower pores (mesopores).

274
 275 **Figure 2.** N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms at -196 °C for prepared catalysts

276 The morphology differences observed in Ref materials depending on the Ni
 277 incorporation method is also reflected in the N₂ uptake. Low N₂ adsorption is obtained for
 278 Ni/CeO₂-Ref sample, denoting low porosity because of its smooth surface, whereas some

279 mesoporosity is obtained in Ni-Ce Ref one as results of its rough and cracked surface. The
280 Ni incorporation method also affects to the definition of the macroporous structure (3DOM),
281 as was observed by FESEM, and consequently, higher adsorption uptakes are observed for
282 samples in which Ni is incorporated prior to the formation of the 3DOM structures (Ni-Ce
283 3DOM and 3DOM CeO₂/Ni), mainly by coimpregnation method (Ni-Ce 3DOM), whereas the
284 addition of Ni after the formation of the 3DOM structure (Ni/CeO₂ 3DOM) does not affect the
285 textural properties of the support (CeO₂ 3DOM), which could indicate that, in this case, these
286 Ni particles are mainly located on the surface of the CeO₂ 3DOM support without blocking the
287 entrance to the pores measured by N₂ adsorption.

288 These observations were corroborated by Hg porosimetry (Figure 3). As expected, a
289 bimodal pore size distribution is presented in 3DOM catalysts with two maxima centred at
290 pore radii of 40 and 80 nm, corresponding to the interstitial spaces and to the porosity
291 obtained by calcination of PMMA spheres, respectively, which agrees with the pore
292 distribution obtained by analysing the FESEM images (Figure 1h). Note also that, according
293 to N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms, the Ni-Ce 3DOM catalyst is the one with the most
294 developed meso and macroporosity (V2 and V3, Table 1), while the rest have very similar
295 pore volumes (Table 1). These peaks are not observed in the case of Ref catalysts; however,
296 it is observed that a small peak is obtained at radii of 4-5 nm for Ni-Ce Ref catalyst that is
297 consistent with the hysteresis loop observed by N₂ adsorption-desorption.

298
299 **Figure 3.** Pore size distributions determined by mercury intrusion porosimetry.

300 **Table 1.** Results of the catalysts characterization by N₂ adsorption, Hg porosimetry and XRD.

Sample	S _{B.E.T.} (m ² /g)	V ₂ (cm ³ /g)*	V ₃ (cm ³ /g)*	D (nm)	a (nm)
3DOM CeO ₂	31	0.03	0.30	14	0.5423
Ni/CeO ₂ 3DOM	31	0.03	0.33	15	0.5415
Ni-Ce 3DOM	46	0.06	0.43	7	0.5415
3DOM CeO ₂ /Ni	31	0.03	0.34	8	0.5415
Ni/CeO ₂ Ref	10	0.01	0.01	22	0.5423
Ni-Ce Ref	56	0.02	0.01	8	0.5415

301 *V₂ and V₃ correspond to the mesopores and macropores volumes obtained by Hg
302 porosimetry, respectively.
303
304
305

306 The crystalline structure of the catalysts has been studied by X-ray diffraction (XRD).
307 Figure 4 shows the diffractograms of all the synthesized catalysts together with the 3DOM
308 CeO₂ support that was used as reference standard. In all cases, CeO₂ phase possesses a
309 cubic fluorite type crystal structure (JCPDS 00-034-0394), and the lattice parameters (a,
310 Table 1) are very similar for all samples and are consistent with the value reported in the
311 JCPDS database (0.5411 nm), indicating that there is no insertion of nickel cations in the
312 CeO₂ lattice. Nickel cations are smaller (0.069 nm for Ni²⁺ and 0.056 nm for Ni³⁺)^[30,31] than
Ce⁴⁺ (0.097 nm)^[32], and their insertion would produce a deformation of the crystal lattice that

313 would be reflected by the decrease of this parameter. Characteristic peaks of NiO (JCPDS
314 01-075-0269) are also observed in the catalysts, and the intensity of those peaks depends
315 on the Ni incorporation method employed. The worst dispersion is obtained by impregnation
316 of Ni on the previously synthesized supports (Ni/3DOM CeO₂ and Ni/CeO₂-Ref) while the
317 incorporation of Ni prior to the formation of the ceria structure favors the Ni-dispersion, to a
318 greater extent in the case of coimpregnation method (Ni-Ce 3DOM and Ni-Ce Ref) as would
319 be expected. Moreover, note that the incorporation of Ni prior to the formation of the CeO₂
320 structure affects the crystallinity of the CeO₂ phase; the diffraction peaks become wider and
321 less intense indicating the stabilization of smaller crystals (see D values , Table 1), which
322 suggests a sintering prevention during the subsequent calcination step. However, the
323 deposition of Ni after the formation of the CeO₂ structure (Ni/CeO₂ 3DOM and Ni/CeO₂ Ref)
324 does not affect the CeO₂ crystal size. This effect can be a consequence of the Ni-CeO₂
325 interaction, indicating a better and intimate contact in samples prepared by incorporation of
326 Ni prior to the formation of the CeO₂ structure.

327
328 **Figure 4.** X-Ray diffractograms of the catalysts. Labeled peaks belong to CeO₂ (▲) and NiO
329 (●) phases.

330 The surface chemistry of catalysts was analysed by XPS. Ni_{2p_{3/2}} core level spectra of
331 fresh and reduced catalysts are depicted in Figure 5a and 5b, respectively, and the relative
332 contribution of each peak is collected in Figure 6. The Ni_{2p_{3/2}} spectral region (Figure 5)
333 shows a main band in the range 851–859 eV together with a satellite structure at higher BE
334 (859–866 eV). The assignment of Ni_{2p} peaks is still a matter of debate, but it has been
335 proposed that the nature of the nickel species can be inferred from the peaks of greater
336 intensity [33,34]. According to literature, the main peaks centred at 852.3, 853.4 and 856.7 eV
337 can be assigned to metallic Ni, NiO, and Ni₂O₃, respectively [33,35–37]. The peak at 856.0 eV
338 can be also attributed to surface Ni³⁺ species associated to the presence of Ni²⁺ vacancies in
339 NiO crystal lattices [35], which is close to the binding energy of Ni₂O₃ and Ni(OH)₂ [38].

340

341

Figure 5. Ni_{2p_{3/2}} core level spectra of a) fresh and b) reduced catalysts.

342

343 Regarding fresh catalysts (Figure 5a), three peaks are observed in the main region
344 centred at around 853.2, 855.0 and 857.2 eV, which can be assigned to surface Ni^{2+} species
345 in NiO structure (surface NiO species), Ni^{2+} species in intimate contact with ceria surface
346 (NiO-Ce species) [38] and Ni^{3+} or $\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2$ species, respectively. This suggests that two NiO
347 active centres of different nature are present in the prepared Ni/CeO₂ catalysts. The
348 proportion of each active site depends on the Ni incorporation method. This proportion is
349 shown in Figure 6a. It is observed that the proportion of $\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2$ or Ni^{3+} species is constant in
350 all 3DOM samples (around 35%), while the proportion of surface NiO and NiO in intimate
351 contact varies depending on the Ni incorporation method. The catalyst prepared by
352 impregnation (Ni/CeO₂ 3DOM) presents the highest proportion of surface NiO (25.4%) and,
353 therefore, the least amount of NiO in intimate contact. This percentage of surface NiO
354 decreases if Ni is incorporated prior to the 3DOM formation at the expense of an increase of
355 the Ni^{2+} species in intimate contact (NiO-Ce), being the catalyst prepared by successive
356 impregnations (3DOM CeO₂/Ni) the one that presents the greatest contact between ceria and
357 Ni phases. Low amount of $\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2$ or Ni^{3+} species is observed in Ref samples as well as a
358 less interaction between Ni and Ce phases regarding similar 3DOM materials (higher NiO
359 proportions, peak at 853.2 eV Figure 6a).

360 The amount of Ni on the surface and the dispersion obtained also depend on the Ni-
361 incorporation method (Table 2). The real percentage of Ni incorporated in the catalysts (Ni %
362 determined by ICP-OES, Ni_{ICP}) is very similar for all catalysts, and very closed to the
363 theoretical value (around 8.5 %), which allows easy comparison of the catalytic results. .
364 Ni_{XPS} contents are closed to real values (Ni_{ICP}) in catalysts prepared by successive
365 impregnation and coimpregnation, which manifests a high dispersion of Ni particles along the
366 ceria matrix, as was also confirmed by XRD. Nonetheless, Ni_{XPS} content is higher than the
367 real value (Ni_{ICP}) for impregnated Ref sample, denoting accumulation of Ni particles on the
368 external surface of ceria. Conversely, this Ni_{XPS} content is lower than the real value for
369 impregnated 3DOM catalyst, indicating that some Ni-particles are located inside the porosity
370 (macroporosity) of CeO₂ 3DOM support, being not detected by XPS.

371

372

373

374 **Figure 6.** XPS results of fresh and reduced catalysts: percentage of each components used
375 to fit the Ni2p_{3/2} spectral region.

376 Analyzing the proportion of Ce³⁺ (Table 2), it is observed that the presence of Ni
377 favors the reduction of ceria, increasing the amount of Ce³⁺ in surface in the catalysts against
378 the support (38 versus 33%). It is also observed that there is a relationship between the
379 amount of Ce³⁺ and the Ni incorporation method and therefore, with the contact between

380 both phases. In this way, the Ni-Ce catalysts (Ref and 3DOM) and 3DOM CeO₂/Ni presents
 381 higher Ce³⁺ content than catalysts prepared by impregnation. As mentioned throughout this
 382 manuscript, the best contact is achieved by simultaneous incorporation of both phases
 383 during the synthesis. Moreover, note that the 3DOM structure favors the reduction of CeO₂
 384 support; a higher percentage of Ce³⁺ is obtained in 3DOM catalysts regarding Ref ones,
 385 denoting a surface oxygen deficiency in the former. This higher surface oxygen vacancies is
 386 ascribed to the presence of PMMA template, because during calcination, an O₂-poor
 387 environment is expected due to oxygen consumption by PMMA combustion and external O₂
 388 diffusion restrictions inside the solid.

389 **Tabla 2.** Surface composition (wt. %) of fresh and reduced catalysts determined by XPS and
 390 total Ni content determined by ICP-OES.

Catalyst	ICP-OES Ni	XPS									
		Fresh					Reduced				
		C	O	Ni	Ce	*Ce ³⁺	C	O	Ni	Ce	Ce ³⁺
CeO ₂ 3DOM	-	9.6	20.7	0.0	69.8	32.9	-	-	-	-	-
Ni/CeO ₂ 3DOM	10.4	10.6	20.8	8.8	59.9	36.8	8.4	19.7	5.6	66.4	37.2
Ni-Ce 3DOM	8.4	11.8	21.9	8.9	57.5	37.8	8.6	20.7	10.1	60.6	32.8
3DOM CeO ₂ /Ni	8.3	13.6	22.3	7.9	56.2	37.4	13.8	20.6	7.2	58.5	32.6
Ni/CeO ₂ Ref	8.8	8.0	22.7	17.4	52.7	29.9	12.0	20.7	10.8	56.6	39.4
Ni-Ce Ref	8.2	13.1	19.7	9.0	58.2	30.3	8.8	18.3	10.8	62.1	34.4

391 Regarding reduced catalysts, three peaks are also observed at 852.6, 854.8 and
 392 857.3 eV (Figure 5b). After reduction, peaks assigned to Ni²⁺ species in NiO structure and
 393 Ni²⁺ species in intimate contact shift to lower binding energy, denoting an electron-
 394 enrichment of Ni species caused by the reduction treatment. However, this peaks shift is
 395 more significant in Reference materials reflecting, again, less interaction between Ni and
 396 CeO₂ phases. The peaks distribution is also affected by the reduction treatment (Figure 6b).
 397 A decrease of Ni³⁺ or Ni(OH)₂ species is observed together with an increase of Ni species in
 398 intimate contact. Ni(OH)₂ species can be decomposed to NiO after the reduction treatment,
 399 which occurs at around 300 °C [39]. With respect to reduced Ni species (Peak at 852.6 eV,
 400 Figure 6b), differences are observed between samples in which Ni is incorporated by
 401

402 impregnation of the support (Ni/CeO₂ Ref and Ni/CeO₂ 3DOM) and samples prepared by
403 coimpregnation (Ni-Ce Ref and Ni-Ce 3DOM) or successive impregnation (3DOM CeO₂/Ni).
404 The amount of reducible Ni species (Peak at 852.6 eV, Figure 6b) decreased after the
405 reduction treatment in samples prepared by direct impregnation of the supports whereas this
406 peak is more or less constant in samples prepared by coimpregnation and successive
407 impregnation. It seems that Ni-Ce contact is improved after the thermal reduction in
408 impregnated samples whereas no modification is obtained in the other catalysts. The strong
409 metal-support interaction (SMSI) effect of ceria is well known [40,41]. It has been well
410 established that through high temperature reduction, oxide moieties from the ceria support
411 migrate over the metallic particles, blocking the surface and modifying its adsorption and
412 catalytic properties [40,41]. The partial encapsulation of Ni particles by reduced ceria can
413 explain the increase of the metal support interaction. As a result of this partial encapsulation,
414 lower Ni wt. % obtained by XPS could be expected. Surface composition of fresh and
415 reduced catalysts determined by XPS is collected in Table 2. Surface Ni wt. % detected by
416 XPS strongly decreases upon the reduction treatment in samples prepared by impregnation
417 of the supports, denoting this partial encapsulation, whereas it remains constant in catalysts
418 prepared by coimpregnation or successive impregnation. Note also that Ce³⁺ amount
419 increases after the reduction treatment in impregnated samples, because of the easy
420 reduction of ceria moieties in the surface. Consequently, the mobility of these reduced ceria
421 moieties seems to be avoided by the intimate NiO-Ceria contact in samples prepared by
422 coimpregnation or successive impregnation. This mobility impediment explains the sintering
423 prevention during the subsequent calcination step observed by XRD (Figure 4) in samples in
424 which the incorporation of Ni was performed prior to the formation of the CeO₂ structure.

425 The reducibility of catalysts must be affected by the different NiO-ceria contact
426 observed by XPS. Therefore, Temperature Programmed Reduction experiments with H₂ (H₂-
427 TPR) were carried out to the fresh catalysts, and results are shown in Figure 7. The H₂-TPR
428 profile of the CeO₂ 3DOM support presents two peaks at 560 °C and 780 °C that can be

429 attributed to the reduction of Ce^{4+} cations in the ceria surface and into the bulk, respectively.
430 Conversely, CeO_2 -Ref shows only the reduction of Ce^{4+} cations localized into the bulk ceria,
431 which indicates that the surface of the 3DOM samples is easier reduced than that of the Ref
432 samples, in line with XPS results. TPR profiles of the corresponding Ni/ CeO_2 catalysts show,
433 in addition to the CeO_2 reduction peaks (shift to lower temperature), the peaks corresponding
434 to the reduction of Ni species at 350 °C. Differences are observed in this peak (Figure 7)
435 depending on the support used (3DOM or Ref) and the Ni incorporation method. NiO
436 reduction symmetrical peaks are obtained in Ref catalysts, while wider and non-symmetrical
437 TPR peaks are observed in 3DOM ones. A peak at 350 °C is obtained in impregnated
438 catalysts (Ni/ CeO_2 Ref and Ni/ CeO_2 3DOM) ascribed to the reduction of Ni^{2+} species.
439 However, a shoulder at higher temperature appears in the 3DOM sample Ni/ CeO_2 3DOM
440 along with the reduction peak at 560 °C, ascribed to surface Ce^{4+} reduction. This shoulder
441 can be assigned to the Ni-catalyzed reduction of Ce^{4+} cations in the ceria surface, which is
442 favored by the easily reduced ceria surface in 3DOM samples with regard to Ref ceria. This
443 Ni-catalyzed surface ceria reduction was already observed by XPS, and could be indicative
444 of the better NiO-Ceria contact observed for 3DOM samples, even in impregnated samples.

445 In the case of the catalysts obtained by the incorporation of Ni prior to the formation of
446 the ceria structure, a widening and a shift of the Ni reduction peak at higher temperatures are
447 observed, while the reduction peak of Ce^{4+} cations in the ceria surface almost disappears,
448 which denotes a better contact between both phases in these catalysts. This shift and
449 widening follow the trend 3DOM CeO_2/Ni > Ni-Ce 3DOM > Ni-Ce Ref > Ni/ CeO_2 Ref ~
450 Ni/ CeO_2 3DOM, which matches the trend observed for NiO in intimate contact observed by
451 XPS and consequently, this displacement is indicative of the contact between Ni and ceria
452 phases.

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Figure 7. H₂-TPR characterization of the catalysts.

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Quantitative calculations were performed using the area under the reduction peaks and a reference CuO sample, and results are collected in Table 3. For Ni/CeO₂ Ref, the consumption of H₂ exactly matches the amount required for 100 % reduction of Ni²⁺ to Ni⁰. However, the consumption of H₂ is slightly higher than the amount required to reduce all nickel on the catalyst assuming the presence of Ni²⁺ for Ni/CeO₂ 3DOM, which evidences that Ce⁴⁺ cations are also reduced in this wide double peak. This H₂ consumption increase is more significant in catalysts in which Ni is incorporated prior to the ceria formation, being more significant for 3DOM samples, corroborating the Ni-catalyzed reduction of surface ceria.

Table 3. Estimation from H₂ consumption in H₂-TPR experiments of the percentage of nickel reduced assuming the presence of Ni²⁺ cations on the catalysts.

Sample	% Ni reduced
Ni/CeO ₂ 3DOM	113
Ni-Ce 3DOM	133
3DOM CeO ₂ /Ni	143
Ni/CeO ₂ Ref	100
Ni-Ce Ref	121

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3.2. Catalytic methanation of CO₂

469 CO₂ conversion and CH₄ selectivity are depicted in Figure 8a and b, respectively. The
470 conversion curves are qualitatively similar, increasing with temperature until a maximum
471 value which is limited by the thermodynamic equilibrium of the methanation reaction. The
472 temperature required to achieve 50% of CO₂ conversion (T50) follows the trend Ni/CeO₂ Ref
473 (294 °C) < Ni-Ce Ref (324 °C) < Ni-Ce 3DOM (393 °C) < 3DOM CeO₂/Ni (> 500 °C) <
474 Ni/CeO₂ 3DOM (>> 500 °C). The selectivity to CH₄ decreases following the same trend,
475 being Ni/CeO₂ Ref the most and Ni/CeO₂ 3DOM the least productive catalyst. In all cases,
476 selectivity to methane decreases from 400 °C since endothermic RWGS reaction (CO₂ + H₂
477 ↔ CO + H₂O) is favored and hence, CH₄ yield decreases at the expense of CO production.

478 This different catalytic behavior seems to be, a priori, related to the NiO-Ceria
479 contact, and consequently, the proportion of reduced Ni sites and NiO in intimate contact
480 with ceria. Two mechanisms have been proposed for the CO₂ methanation reaction, which
481 are referred to as associative and dissociative^[42]. In the associative mechanism, CO₂ is
482 chemisorbed without dissociation and subsequently, hydrogenated in two consecutive stages
483 eliminating one oxygen per step. In contrast, in the dissociative method (the most common
484 with ceria catalysts), CO₂ is dissociatively adsorbed followed by hydrogenation to methane.
485 For ceria based catalysts it has been proposed that reduced cerium cations (Ce³⁺) are highly
486 active sites for the chemisorption and dissociation of CO₂. The Ce³⁺ sites are oxidized to Ce⁴⁺
487 after the dissociation of CO₂ and, therefore, must be reduced again by the H₂ close to the
488 active centres. Therefore, to analyze the catalytic results, two active centres should be taken
489 into account: i) species of Ni in close contact with ceria that are highly active for the
490 dissociation of CO₂ and ii) reduced Ni⁰ where the dissociation of H₂ takes place.

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493 **Figure 8.** Catalytic methanation of CO₂. a) CO₂ conversion and b) CH₄ selectivity.

494 As it was pointed out by XPS and H₂-TPR, the proportion of surface Ni and NiO in
 495 intimate contact with ceria depends on the Ni-incorporation method and on the reducibility of
 496 ceria surface, which is affected by the 3DOM structure. The addition of Ni prior to the
 497 synthesis of CeO₂ structure generates a high proportion of NiO in intimate contact with ceria,
 498 which improves the reducibility of the ceria surface (Ce³⁺ sites) whereas less contact and

499 lower Ni-catalyzed reducibility (Table 3) is obtained for impregnated samples. Consequently,
500 the former presents a high amount of active sites where CO_2 dissociation takes place,
501 whereas the latter present high amount of active sites for H_2 dissociation. Thus, the Ni/3DOM
502 CeO_2 catalyst has a high number of centres for the dissociation and transfer of H_2 , but not
503 enough for the dissociation of CO_2 , while the contrary occurs for 3DOM CeO_2/Ni catalyst.
504 Hence, an optimal proportion of both sites is required to achieve the maximum conversion of
505 CO_2 : around 25% of surface Ni for H_2 dissociation and 75% of NiO in intimate contact with
506 ceria for the CO_2 dissociation (Figure 9). When increasing NiO in intimate contact to higher
507 level, the CO_2 dissociation is improved, but the dissociation and transfer of H_2 is hindered
508 and, as consequence, part of this chemisorbed CO_2 is again desorbed as CO_2 or CO without
509 hydrogenation taking place. Thus, CO_2 conversion decreases and CO production increases
510 (Figure 8b), e.g. as for 3DOM CeO_2/Ni catalyst. If surface Ni increases, the transfer of
511 dissociated H atoms to the chemisorbed CO is favored, increasing the activity and selectivity
512 to methane. Above 25% of surface Ni, the dissociation of CO_2 is restricted in a H-rich
513 environment, and therefore, the activity is limited by the CO_2 dissociation, i.e. Ni-Ce Ref and
514 Ni/ CeO_2 3DOM.

515

516 **Figure 9.** Relationship between the activity per surface active centre (Ni atom determined by
517 XPS) at 400 °C and the proportion of surface Ni⁰ determined by XPS for reduced catalysts.
518 This proportion has been calculated taking into account only Ni⁰ and NiO species.

519 The stability of catalysts was also studied. Stability tests were performed using the
520 optimal catalyst (Ni/CeO₂ Ref) at two different temperatures, 300 and 350 °C. A high stability
521 is observed after 24 h at both temperatures with a loss of activity lower than 3% (Figure 10).
522 Nonetheless, note that this activity loss is ten time higher at 300 °C (2.5%) than at 350 °C
523 (0.25%). The reduction temperature of Ni species is 340 °C (Figure 7) and consequently,
524 reduced Ni species are oxidized during the reaction at 300 °C decreasing the activity for CO₂
525 methanation. Conversely, Ni species are able to be reduced again during the reaction at 350
526 °C and the activity loss is not significant in this case.

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Ni/CeO ₂ Ref	12.0	20.7	10.8	56.6	39.4	10.0	21.7	11.2	57.1	34.5
Ni-Ce Ref	8.8	18.3	10.8	62.1	34.4	10.7	22.8	9.4	57.1	37.8

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547 **Figure 11.** XPS characterization in the energy region of Ni2p transition for reduced and used
 548 catalysts for a) Ni/CeO₂ Ref and b) Ni-Ce Ref.

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551 3.3. *In situ* DRIFTS experiments

552 In situ DRIFTS experiments were carried out in order to obtain additional information
 553 about the reaction mechanism, and the most active catalysts (Ni/CeO₂ Ref and Ni-Ce Ref)
 554 have been selected for these experiments. Figure 12 shows the spectra recorded at different
 555 temperatures after 60 minutes under reaction conditions, and a background recorded at
 556 room temperature in He has been subtracted in all cases. Several regions can be
 557 distinguished in all spectra. The intense band around 2400 cm⁻¹ belongs to gas phase CO₂,
 558 above 3500 cm⁻¹ are observed bands of O-H bonds in hydroxyls or bicarbonates, and below
 559 1700 cm⁻¹ can be distinguished bands that can potentially be assigned to carbonate,
 560 bicarbonate or formate species ^[43–49].

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 571 **Figure 12.** In situ DRIFTS experiments under H₂/CO₂/He at different temperatures. a)
 572 Ni/CeO₂ Ref and b) Ni-Ce Ref. Spectra were recorded after 60 min under reaction conditions.

573
 574 The most active catalyst (Ni/CeO₂ Ref; Figure 12a) shows bands at 150 °C that are
 575 consistent with the presence of monodentate and bidentate carbonates. These species are
 576 created by CO₂ chemisorption, and are detected in the spectrum at 150 °C because the
 577 reaction temperature is too low for taking place the methanation reaction (see catalytic tests
 578 in Figure 9). However, the bands disappear above 250 °C, and the negative bands observed
 579 indicate that carbonates present on the catalyst surface at room temperature in He (in the
 580 background spectra conditions) are removed during methanation. These in situ experiments
 581 allow concluding that the surface of this catalyst (Ni/CeO₂ Ref), which combines the optimum
 582 proportion of active sites for CO₂ and H₂ dissociation, remains clean during the reaction.

583 However, this is not the case on the Ni-Ce Ref catalyst, which is slightly less active.
 584 As deduced from XPS (Figure 5), the Ni-Ce Ref catalyst has a higher proportion of actives
 585 sites for CO₂ chemisorption than sites for H₂ dissociation, and the consequence of this
 586 imbalance of active sites affects the surface carbon species observed under reaction

587 conditions (Figure 12b). At 150 °C is observed the presence of monodentate and bidentate
588 carbonates, in agreement with Ni/CeO₂, and these species are depleted at higher
589 temperatures. However, for the Ni-Ce Ref catalyst the surface is not completely clean under
590 reaction conditions, but bicarbonate bands are observed because the chemisorption of CO₂
591 is favored with regard to H₂ dissociation, which limits further hydrogenation.

592

593 3.4. Pulse experiments with isotopic CO₂

594 Pulse experiments with isotopic ¹³C¹⁸O₂ were performed with Ni/CeO₂ Ref and Ni-Ce
595 Ref at 350°C, and the conclusions are consistent with the DRIFTS experiments. Figure 13
596 shows, as an example, the profiles of the signals detected during the first pulse of ¹³C¹⁸O₂ to
597 each catalyst previously stabilized in a H₂/He flow at the reaction temperature. The profile of
598 Ar obtained in a previous pulse of this gas is also included to have a reference of the peak
599 shape for a gas without chemical interaction with the catalysts.

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Figure 13. First pulse of Ar and ¹³C¹⁸O₂ at 350 °C over a) Ni/CeO₂ Ref and b) Ni-Ce Ref.

606 Different peaks of CO₂, CO and CH₄ species are observed in the same position than
607 the Ar peak. The area of these peaks depends on the reaction conversion and selectivity,
608 and their position evidences that the reaction steps involved in their creation are fast.
609 However, a broad H₂¹⁶O band appears delayed with regard to the other peaks, indicating that
610 water desorption is much slower than the other steps.

611 Note than all oxygen-containing species detected in Figure 13 come with ¹⁶O, which
612 belongs to catalyst oxygen, while ¹⁸O from the pulsed ¹³C¹⁸O₂ is retained on the catalysts.
613 This evidences that the chemisorption of ¹³C¹⁸O₂ leads to a fast dissociation of the oxygen,
614 and the carbon species left are either hydrogenated to CH₄ or reoxidized with catalyst
615 oxygen.

616 On the contrary, carbon species with ¹³C and ¹²C are detected, and this means that
617 not only carbon of the pulsed ¹³C¹⁸O₂ reacts but also the surface carbon species previously
618 present on the catalysts. This is consistent with the DRIFTS spectra that provided evidences
619 of the removal of carbon surface species present on the catalysts before the catalytic
620 experiments.

621 For quantitative analysis of the pulse experiments, the area under the peaks was
622 integrated and the amount of each specie was calculated. Figure 14 shows results of these
623 calculations, expressed as mass balance of carbon, for three consecutive pulses of ¹³C¹⁸O₂.

624 The most active catalyst (Ni/CeO₂ Ref) shows the same behavior during the three
625 pulses (Figure 14a). The ¹³C¹⁸O₂ pulsed is consumed and CH₄ is released as reaction
626 product, as expected. Both ¹²CH₄ and ¹³CH₄ are detected, confirming that hydrogenation not
627 only occurs on carbon species created upon ¹³C¹⁸O₂ chemisorption but also on previously
628 chemisorbed species. In addition, an important proportion of ¹³C¹⁶O₂ is observed, and this
629 evidences the exchange of oxygen atoms between the gas molecules and the catalyst. Note
630 that the proportion of species with ¹⁸O is negligible, evidencing that the catalyst oxygen is
631 highly involved in the reaction. This is also observed in the H₂O molecules (Figure 15), all of
632 them coming with catalyst oxygen. Controversially, CO species are also observed in Figure
633 14a, while the catalytic tests were 100% selective towards CH₄ formation, and this apparent

634 disagreement is due to the different experimental conditions of the catalytic tests and pulse
 635 experiments. In the catalytic tests, CO₂ and H₂ concentrations are in stoichiometric proportion
 636 while a large excess of H₂ is used in the pulse experiments.

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638

639 **Figure 14.** Percentage of carbon species in three consecutive pulses of ¹³C¹⁸O₂ at 350 °C
 640 over a) Ni/CeO₂ Ref and b) Ni-Ce Ref.

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643 The behavior of the catalyst Ni-Ce Ref (Figure 14b) is not stable in consecutive
644 pulses. The first pulse yields a high proportion of $^{12}\text{CH}_4$ and $^{12}\text{CO}_2$, that is, the carbon species
645 present on the catalyst before the $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}_2$ pulse react first, and ^{13}C -containing species are
646 observed in further cycles. This difference between Ni/CeO₂ Ref and Ni-Ce Ref confirms
647 once more that the most active catalyst (Ni/CeO₂) is more effective hydrogenating the
648 surface carbon species, and that is very important to optimize the proportion of active sites
649 for CO₂ and H₂ dissociation in order to optimize the methanation activity.

650

651 **Figure 15.** Percentage of H₂O species in three consecutive pulses of $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}_2$ at 350 °C over
652 a) Ni/CeO₂ Ref and b) Ni-Ce Ref.
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656 **4. Conclusions**

657 In this work Ni/CeO₂ catalysts have been prepared and optimized in order to obtain an
658 optimum performance in the CO₂ methanation reaction. To achieve this goal, the Ni
659 incorporation method and the surface of the ceria support was varied in order to modify Ni-
660 Ce interaction. In this sense, three dimensionally ordered macroporous (3DOM) structures
661 have been synthesized and Ni introduced during the 3DOM synthesis by i) coimpregnation;
662 ii) successive impregnation of Ni and Ce precursors or iii) Ni impregnation after CeO₂ 3DOM
663 synthesis . Materials with uncontrolled structures (named Ref) were also prepared by
664 coprecipitation and Ni impregnation. From all the above results and discussion, the following
665 conclusions can be drawn:

666 i) The introduction of nickel during the formation of the 3DOM structure, Ni-Ce 3DOM and
667 3DOM CeO₂/Ni, favors the Ni-dispersion and improves the definition of the macroporous
668 structure.

669 ii) XRD results indicate that Ni is not incorporated into the ceria lattice in any case but the
670 incorporation of Ni prior to the formation of the CeO₂ structure affects the crystallinity of the
671 CeO₂ phase; stabilizing smaller crystals suggests a sintering prevention during the
672 subsequent calcination step. However, the deposition of Ni after the formation of the CeO₂
673 structure does not affect the CeO₂ crystal size.

674 iii) XPS pointed out that Ni/CeO₂ catalyst combines two types of active sites: NiO-Ceria
675 interface and reduced Ni⁰ particles efficient for CO₂ and H₂ dissociation, respectively. The
676 proportion of surface Ni⁰ and NiO-Ceria varies depending on the Ni incorporation method and
677 surface area of the support. The catalysts prepared by impregnation (Ni/CeO₂ 3DOM and
678 Ni/CeO₂-Ref) present higher proportion of surface Ni⁰ and, therefore, the least amount of NiO
679 in intimate contact. This percentage of surface NiO decreases if Ni is incorporated before to
680 the formation of the CeO₂ structure at the expense of an increase of the NiO-Ceria interface,

681 being the catalyst prepared by successive impregnations (3DOM CeO₂/Ni) the one that
682 presents the greatest contact between ceria and Ni phases.

683 iv) The reducibility of catalysts is also affected by the different NiO-Ceria contact observed by
684 XPS. Ni-catalyzed reduction of Ce⁴⁺ cations in the ceria surface is observed in samples with
685 high NiO-Ceria interface. This Ni-catalyzed surface ceria reduction was already observed by
686 XPS and could be indicative of the better NiO-Ceria contact observed.

687 v) The catalytic behavior is related to the NiO-Ceria contact, and consequently, the
688 proportion of reduced Ni⁰ sites and NiO in intimate contact with ceria. The addition of Ni prior
689 to the synthesis of CeO₂ structure generates a high proportion of NiO in intimate contact with
690 ceria, and thus, a high number of active sites where CO₂ dissociation takes place, whereas
691 the incorporation by impregnation generates high number of active sites for H₂ dissociation.
692 Both cases lead to a low CO₂ conversion. An optimal proportion of both sites is required to
693 achieve the maximum conversion of CO₂: around 25% of surface Ni⁰ for H₂ dissociation and
694 75% of NiO-Ceria interface for the CO₂ dissociation.

695 vi) In situ DRIFTS experiments allow concluding that the surface of the catalyst (Ni/CeO₂
696 Ref), which combines the optimum proportion of active sites for CO₂ and H₂ dissociation
697 remains clean during the reaction. However, this is not the case on the Ni-Ce Ref catalyst,
698 which has a higher proportion of active sites for CO₂ chemisorption than sites for H₂
699 dissociation, This imbalance of active sites has consequences in the surface carbon species
700 observed under reaction conditions and thus, in the catalytic activity.

701 vii) Pulse experiments with isotopic CO₂ confirmed once more that the most active catalyst
702 (Ni/CeO₂-Ref) is more effective hydrogenating the surface carbon species, and that is very
703 important to optimize the proportion of active sites for CO₂ and H₂ dissociation in order to
704 optimize the methanation activity.

705

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717

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